

Integration, Cataloguing and Management of Biobanking and Clinical Data Using FAIR Genomes Metadata Schema

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ABSTRACT

In the dynamic environment of hospitals, valuable real-world data often remain underutilised despite their potential to revolutionize cancer research and personalised medicine. This study explores the challenges and opportunities in managing hospital-generated data, particularly within the Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute (MMCI) in Brno, Czech Republic. Utilizing Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) technology, MMCI generates substantial volumes of genomic data. Due to inadequate curation, these data remain difficult to integrate with clinical records for secondary use (such as personalised treatment outcome prediction and patient stratification based on their genomic profiles). This paper proposes solutions based on the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) to enhance data sharing and reuse. The primary output of our work is the development of an automated pipeline that continuously processes and integrates NGS data with clinical and biobank information upon their creation. It stores the data in a special secured repository for sensitive data in a structured form to ensure smooth retrieval.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the busy hospital environment, essential data are often overlooked amidst the daily hustle of patient care and medical procedures. These real-world data, generated, for example, through DNA sequencing technologies, hold the key to unlocking new insights into cancer biology, personalised treatment approaches, and therapeutic innovations [1]. However, in many practices, this valuable information is often confined to diagnostic reports haphazardly stored on laboratory hard drives. As a result, this data remains mostly unprocessed, disorganised, and not connected to clinical records, making it hard to access or link with other datasets. This disjointed approach to data management, accompanied by other obstacles [2], prevents realising the full potential of genomic information in cancer care and poses significant barriers to translational research and precision medicine initiatives.

In this context, there is an urgent need for transformative solutions to streamline hospital data acquisition, curation, and integration. Such solutions would enable a more cohesive, data-driven approach to cancer treatment and research. This article explores the current challenges in data management at a leading Czech oncology institute and proposes novel strategies to enhance the secondary use of hospital-generated data.

2. BACKGROUND

Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute (MMCI)^① in Brno is a leading institution in cancer patients' treatment in the Czech Republic. The rapid development of sequencing technologies in recent decades has opened up the possibility of their direct use in managing cancer patients. Thus, in 2019, MMCI initiated a multidisciplinary molecular tumour board to provide expert input for patients with tumours. It is an interdisciplinary group of experts responsible for systematically interpreting large amounts of sequencing data and combining them with clinical data and all other patient-related characteristics to set optimal treatment recommendations. MMCI uses sequencing technology called Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) [3], which generates sequencing data of up to 40 GB per output folder. This NGS data have been stored longitudinally at the MMCI but is poorly described and curated. Therefore, sharing the data for secondary usage in translational research or disease recurrence cases is difficult.

MMCI has a well-established biobank [4] where the biological material of patients is stored. The biobank is an integral part of the BBMRI-ERIC^② (Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure–European Research Infrastructure Consortium) infrastructure [5], that provides a coordinated approach to biobanking resources and biomolecular data. Moreover, the Bank of Biological Material MMCI coordinates the Czech national node of biobanks^③ and participates in the development of core BBMRI-ERIC services such as Negotiator [6] or Directory [7]. These services enable streamlined access to samples and efficient data management across the entire infrastructure. The Directory is an online

^① <https://www.mou.cz/en/>

^② <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/>

^③ <https://www.bbmri.cz/>

catalogue of biological samples available within BBMRI biobanks and the Negotiator tool serves as a communication platform for biobanks and researchers requesting samples and any associated data. Following successful negotiations, samples are provided to applicants alongside the agreed-upon clinical information and can be supplemented with additional data types. However, obtaining the requested data is challenging due to the absence of integrated and organised data systems that facilitate efficient retrieval for these purposes. This work was initiated specifically to address these obstacles in a comprehensive manner.

2.1 Related Work

The exponential growth of hospital-generated data in recent years has brought increasing attention to its secondary use for research purposes [8-10]. This trend highlights the immense potential of existing datasets to generate new insights and advance scientific knowledge beyond their original purpose. Aligning with this vision, the European Commission proposed the European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation in May 2022 [11]. This regulation aims to streamline and enhance the reuse of primary and secondary health data, fostering innovation and improving healthcare outcomes through simplified data-sharing mechanisms. The EHDS initiative underscores the critical importance of leveraging health data responsibly and efficiently to support cutting-edge research and policy-making.

In this context, Open Science (OS) [12-14], a concept evolving with technology and national policies [15-16] since the late 1980s, plays a key role by promoting transparent, accessible knowledge shared through collaborative networks, which enhances innovation, education, and efficient use of public funds [17], particularly in healthcare research [13]. In the medical field, the need to share data is clear, but the challenge lies in determining how and when to do so, given the sensitivity of the information. Since healthcare data often involves highly personal and confidential details, careful consideration is required to ensure that sharing is done responsibly and in compliance with privacy regulations [18].

2.1.1 Securing Sensitive Data for Secondary Usage

From the OS and EHDS perspective, our work focuses on the secondary use of hospital-generated data. This involves repurposing data originally collected for clinical purposes rather than research. However, this shift presents several challenges, particularly in sharing sensitive patient data, with data security being a primary concern [19]. However, de-identification techniques can play a crucial role in ensuring data security by safeguarding sensitive information [20]. An inspiring example is the C-BIG repository, developed by Montreal Neurological Institute-Hospital [21], which uses advanced de-identification techniques to protect patient privacy while sharing sensitive data. This repository integrates biospecimens, clinical records, imaging, and genetic data from patients with neurological diseases and healthy controls. It illustrates a scalable approach to overcoming the challenges of sharing sensitive patient data by introducing three data access layers while adhering to the so-called FAIR Principles.

2.1.2 FAIRification

In 2016, the FAIR Principles [22] were introduced to guide researchers on how to make scientific data more open, accessible, and reusable. The goal of FAIR Principles is to provide data discoverability by humans and machines (Findability), information on how to get the data (Accessibility), data integration with other data (Interoperability) and that all leads to the possibility of replicating or combining data in different settings (Reusability).

The process of aligning data with the FAIR Principles, known as the FAIRification process [23], involves several steps: assessing current data workflows, identifying necessary data sources, integrating diverse data, ensuring metadata richness, and implementing data pseudonymisation for security. An essential part of making data interoperable is utilizing interoperable standards [24] and metadata schema together to ensure adequate data description. A metadata schema [25] is a structured framework that facilitates data discovery, access, and integration with other sources. It defines specific metadata elements, their relationships, and the rules for using them, which collectively enable consistent data representation and interoperability. Unique to the field of sharing NGS data is the FAIR Genomes metadata schema [26], developed in the Netherlands by van der Velde, K.J. and his team. This schema is designed to ensure the discoverability of NGS data linked with clinical, personal, and biobank data; however, as of September 2024, according to information provided by its creators, the FAIR Genomes metadata schema has not been implemented in any known practical use cases.

To support the broader application of FAIR principles, FAIR Data Points (FDPs) [27] have been introduced by Luiz Olavo Bonino da Silva Santos and colleagues. FDPs are tools designed to make datasets and metadata available in a standardised, machine-readable format, improving discoverability, accessibility, and reuse.

2.2 Problem Formulation

Our research focuses on enhancing the accessibility and usability of sequencing data alongside biological samples from biobanks. We aim to have information about sequencing data availability linked with samples and clinical information describing the patient and the origin of the samples. Thanks to publishing such complex information in a data catalogue [28], data connected to stored samples is easily findable by researchers who can require access to it and ultimately reuse it. In response to the pressing challenge confronted by MMCI, our work tackles the urgent demand for a robust data storage solution and a reliable backup system, aiming to replace conventional portable storage media and ad hoc cloud services. Our approach entails migrating from manual storage on portable media to utilizing cloud storage infrastructure designed explicitly to manage sensitive data securely.

3. VALUE OF THE DATA

Integrating hospital-generated data, such as NGS, with clinical and biobanking information is incredibly valuable for research. Those data provide crucial insights into individuals' genetic makeup, aiding our understanding of cancer biology while considering other variables such as diagnosis, age, sample material, etc. Combining genetic findings with clinical records and sample-derived data can identify new treatment targets, develop drugs targeting specific genetic changes, and tailor treatment plans to each patient's unique needs and characteristics. Furthermore, successfully integrating and storing this data in a local cloud facilitates federated analyses. For instance, such infrastructure can support studies on rare tumours across the EU, as demonstrated by the IDEA4RC Horizon Europe project^④, in which MMCI participates.

4. DATA ACQUISITION

4.1 Collecting Data

In the initial step of the FAIRification process, we have thoroughly examined the existing data workflows within MMCI, focusing on the exploration and interconnection of (meta)data sources. This phase involved close collaboration with the Department of Oncological Pathology team, who perform sequencing activities regularly. Starting at the beginning of 2022, we conducted multiple interviews and practical demonstrations where the team detailed their internal workflows (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Original Sequencing Data Pipeline at Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute.

④ <https://www.idea4rc.eu/>

Additionally, we worked with a bioinformatician involved in the patient diagnosis process, who comprehensively described the data analysis procedures. Our examination revealed that many routine transfers of NGS data were previously handled manually (see Figure 1). We identified the following NGS, biobanking, and clinical data sources:

- **Sequencing Machines:** Two sequencers, the NextSeq 550[®] and MiSeq[®], produce output folders containing NGS data enriched with technical details about the sequencing run. These folders are automatically uploaded to the BaseSpace Sequence Hub[®] cloud environment provided by Illumina company headquartered in San Diego, California.
- **Analytical Software:** Two software for NGS data analysis are in use: Clinical Genomics Workspace (CGW)[®] for data from the NextSeq 550 and NextGENe[®] for data from the MiSeq sequencer.
- **Laboratory Notebook:** A paper notebook containing detailed information about the sequencing run and its preparation. This source is currently in hand-written form following standard operating procedures (SOPs), though its digitalisation would significantly streamline workflow automation.
- **Hospital Information System (HIS):** HIS stores donor and sample information regularly exported in XML format.

4.2 Data Integration

In the next step, we focused on finding a way to integrate these diverse data sources. We discovered that four different identifiers were used: a patient number, a biopsy number, a sample number and a predictive number. Each patient in our hospital is assigned a patient number (e.g., 284). A patient can undergo multiple biopsies; for instance, in 2022, a patient might have two samples taken, resulting in biopsy numbers 2022/7128-1 for one tissue and 2022/7128-2 for another tissue. In 2023, the same patient might have another biopsy, 2023/3749, with only tissue taken. Each sample is assigned an identifier, e.g. BBM:2023:3749:53, which includes the year, biopsy number, and material type. If the material is sequenced, it receives a predictive number (e.g., 2023_3749), identifying the NGS data. Unfortunately, these identifiers were recorded in various formats, complicating automatic data linkage. For example, a predictive number could appear as either "23/3749", "3749-23", or "23_3749", leading to inconsistency and unreliability. This inconsistency made it challenging to uniquely match sequencing data with the exported HIS patient records. To address this issue, we collaborated with laboratory staff to standardise the method of recording sample identifiers, further ensuring consistency and reliability in data integration.

Furthermore, we identified a critical limitation in the HIS export: the absence of the predictive number, the sole identifier linking sequencing output data to specific patients or samples. To address this issue, we requested that our IT department enhance the export functionality to include this essential identifier. Due to the department's workload and staff shortages, the implementation took longer than anticipated.

[®] <https://www.illumina.com/systems/sequencing-platforms/nextseq.html>

[®] <https://www.illumina.com/systems/sequencing-platforms/miseq/specifications.html>

[®] <https://www.illumina.com/products/by-type/informatics-products/basespace-sequence-hub.html>

[®] <https://www.pierianDX.com/clinical-genomics-workspace-software>

[®] <https://softgenetics.com/products/nextgene/>

Nevertheless, this step was crucial, as it enabled the accurate identification and seamless integration of sequencing data with corresponding patient and sample information.

4.3 Data Processing

A comprehensive data processing approach is crucial for effectively organizing and storing data for secondary use. This approach encompasses several key steps: data cleaning to minimize redundancy and optimize volume, annotation using interoperable vocabularies to facilitate collaboration, and pseudonymization of sensitive information to safeguard patient privacy.

4.3.1 Data Curation

During the data curation phase, we categorised data into two groups: essential data for retention and non-essential data for deletion. Many files generated by Illumina sequencers and analysis applications do not contain vital information for further use. Some files merely confirm the completion of subprocesses, provide detailed technical data irrelevant to researchers, or contain machine-readable data used in communication between the sequencer and the BaseSpace Sequence Hub cloud environment. Conversely, specific files or parts of files provide fundamental information that must be preserved alongside the NGS data. By identifying and separating essential from non-essential files, we effectively reduced the space required for data storage. This step resulted in creating detailed mind maps of MiSeq and NextSeq output folder structures (see Supplementary File 1 and 2) based on Illumina documentation[®] and consulting with laboratory staff.

4.3.2 Metadata Extraction

To ensure comprehensive metadata management, we utilised the FAIR Genomes metadata schema [26] as our template. We meticulously extracted the necessary metadata to populate this schema, ensuring we accurately captured all relevant information. This process involved identifying and documenting metadata elements essential for data interoperability, reuse, and compliance with FAIR principles. By adhering to the FAIR Genomes metadata schema, we standardised our metadata, enhancing the discoverability and utility of our datasets.

We have adopted all nine modules (Study, Personal, Leaflet/consent form, Material, Clinical, Individual consent, Sample preparation, Sequencing, Analysis) of the FAIR Genomes metadata schema and aligned our data with the modules. Our mapping was based on a metadata codebook[®] that meets the requirements of the NICTIZ national standard organisation. The resulting mapping is available in our GitHub repository in Supplementary File 6. The tables in this file summarise detailed information on the given attribute's availability and its example values within MMCI data. Additionally, these tables document the resources used to extract the required metadata and map it to the allowed values for the catalogue,

[®] <https://knowledge.illumina.com/>

[®] <https://decor.nictiz.nl/art-decor/decor-project--fairgenomes->

as defined by the ontologies in the metadata codebook mentioned earlier. All modules, except for the "Leaflet & Consent Form" module, should automatically fill when a new record of a sequencing run is completed. A record for the module "Leaflet & Consent Form" will be created manually when a new version of the consent form is released. We have extended the schema with a few attributes that were not available originally, such as the "Whole Slide Images Availability" attribute in the Material module or "Genes (*all coding regions covered)" within the Sample preparation module. At the same time, we reduced a few attributes from the schema that were not available within MMCI data or seemed irrelevant to our context. We have managed to fill in some attributes completely; however, some attributes are unavailable from MMCI data sources so far. MMCI will adopt a new information system soon, so we expect to fulfil those attributes as part of our further development after more detailed parametrisation within a new HIS is available.

4.3.3 (Meta)data Pseudonymisation

Before storing data in a secure cloud operated by an affiliated computer science institution and exposing metadata in a catalogue, it is inevitable to perform de-identification of data and metadata. To address this issue, two solutions were considered acceptable—either anonymisation or pseudonymisation [20]. The most significant disparity between the two lies in their irreversibility; once data are anonymised, they become irretrievable, whereas pseudonymised data can potentially be re-identified by an authorised individual using supplementary information (a so-called mapping table [29]). Furthermore, pseudonymised data retain its classification as personal data and thus falls under GDPR protection. Because anonymisation requires removing significant personal information, which reduces the data's usefulness for research, we chose pseudonymisation instead. Pseudonymisation involved replacing identifiable information with artificial identifiers, ensuring that sensitive data could not be traced back to individual patients. As we are working with four types of identifiers—a predictive number, a patient number, a sample number and a biopsy number (see Chapter 4.2. *Data Integration*)—we have generated a unique, alphanumeric (32-digit hexadecimal) 128bit pseudonym for every identifier using the UUID (Universal Unique Identifier) v4 [30] algorithm.

There are several ways to create pseudonyms. One method involves using a counter that increments with each new pseudonym, but this approach can suffer from scalability issues and become a bottleneck in parallel processing. Another method is to use cryptographic hash functions or other encryption techniques, which may be vulnerable to brute force attacks and could be broken.

UUID v4 is a randomly generated number that guarantees practical uniqueness. Although, theoretically, a duplicate can occur (e.g., generating 1 billion UUIDs every second for about 100 years results in a 50% chance of a single duplicate [31]), but it is extremely rare in practice. This means there is no need to check if a generated pseudonym exists, which would otherwise become increasingly time-consuming as the database grows. Since UUID v4 is not derived from the original ID through encryption or hashing, de-pseudonymisation is only possible using the mapping table [29].

Since the FAIR Genomes metadata schema requires an identifier for each record within every module, we decided to use the same identifiers for related modules. For example, modules such as Sample Preparation, Sequencing, and Analysis refer to NGS data identified by a predictive number within MMCI. Therefore, we use this predictive number as the basis for creating a pseudonym. We distinguish pseudonyms by attaching a prefix with a keyword such as "sampleprep", "sequencing", or "analysis". Table 1 summarises the MMCI identifiers used to create pseudonyms, and Table 2 provides examples of pseudonyms for each module.

Table 1. Summary of MMCI Identifiers Used within Adopted FAIR Genomes Metadata Schema Modules.

Module	MMCI Identifier	MMCI Identifier Example
Personal	patient number	284
Clinical	biopsy number	2023/3749
Material	sample number	BBM:2023:3749:53
Sample preparation	predictive number	23_3749
Sequencing	predictive number	23_3749
Analysis	predictive number	23_3749
Individual Consent	patient number	284
Leaflet/consent form	consent form version	1
Study	-	-

Table 2. Examples of Pseudonyms Created for Each Module.

Module	Pseudonym
Personal	mmci_patient_06994c64-29de-4dce-a7bd-ca5ed38b1455
Clinical	mmci_clinical_00000000-0000-0000-0000-00000c0c124f
Material	mmci_sample_0fa8461f-2e89-4a76-baad-45099e80a882
Sample preparation	mmci_sampleprep_0b52fdb1-aa9b-465d-8cb2-8e47792b2023
Sequencing	mmci_predictive_0b52fdb1-aa9b-465d-8cb2-8e47792b2023
Analysis	mmci_analysis_0b52fdb1-aa9b-465d-8cb2-8e47792b2023
Individual Consent	mmci_consent_06994c64-29de-4dce-a7bd-ca5ed38b1455
Leaflet/consent form	mmci_consentform_1
Study	-

5. APPLICATION

5.1 FAIRification Process

In this part, we outline the methodology employed for the FAIRification process based on the model introduced by Jacobsen [23]. Initially, we familiarised ourselves with our institution's current workflow and data resources. This initial step involved understanding the format in which our data was expressed, considering used identifiers, and assessing the availability of metadata. Through this preliminary exploration, primarily conducted through interviews with staff members from the Department of Oncological Pathology, Bank of Biological Material or HIS managers, we gained insights into the nature of the data intended for FAIRification.

Next, we conducted a thorough review of existing metadata schemas relevant to discoverability of NGS data. After an extensive search, we selected the FAIR Genomes metadata schema [26] for adoption. This choice was driven by the absence of any other schema capable of adequately describing biobanking data, clinical information, and sequencing data in an integrated manner. While the FAIR Genomes schema has not yet been implemented in any known practical applications, which poses potential challenges, it aligns well with the FAIR principles and meets our requirements.

Following the selection of the schema, we defined the elicited requirements (see Supplementary File 3) using the indirect elicitation technique - document analysis [32]. We reviewed the documentation of various cataloguing software to understand their features and capabilities, which helped us brainstorm and identify the essential functionalities required for our data catalogue. We explored various platforms for metadata exposure and determined that the Molgenis platform [33] was the most suitable to meet our objectives. Finally, we conducted an assessment to evaluate the level of FAIRness achieved by our solution, as recommended by Jacobsen. From the plethora of available tools [34-36] (more than 20 FAIR evaluation tools are currently registered at regularly updated website FAIRassist[®]) we chose to utilize the FAIR Data Maturity Model [37]. This decision was driven by its ability to operate with indicators of varying importance, thus allowing for customisation to reflect our specific context best. The tool defines a set of core assessment criteria for FAIRness to prevent ambiguity and diverse interpretations of FAIR Principles. The detailed results of the FAIR level evaluation of our solution can be found in Supplementary File 8, together with a final graph showing the fulfilment of 41 assessed indicators.

5.2 Technical Implementation

Our work was carried out in two main phases. The first focused on organizing and integrating data into a structured format. The second phase built upon the previous one, involving the creation of a platform for presenting metadata aligned with FAIR principles. We used the open-source Molgenis platform[®] and the FAIR Genomes metadata schema[®], integrating several tools from the FAIR Genomes FAIRification

[®] <https://fairassist.org/>

[®] <https://github.com/molgenis>

[®] <https://github.com/fairgenomes>

framework. This resulted in the BBMRI.cz Data Catalogue, deployed at *data.bbmri.cz*, which facilitates interoperable metadata representation and supports the secondary utilization of hospital-generated data.

These phases led to the development of an automated data pipeline, designed to streamline manual data transfers—a common practice at our institute before data FAIRification. The pipeline was created using Python scripts and is outlined in the flowchart in Supplementary File 7.

5.2.1 Code

The entire data pipeline consists of three main components—Pseudonymiser, Organiser, and Uploader—each corresponding to a dedicated repository responsible for specific tasks, as shown in Table 3. The code for the pipeline is available on our BBMRI.cz GitHub® page, within the core repository, NGS-data-FAIRification®, which serves as a central hub. This repository not only links to the three specialised repositories but also contains essential documentation and supplementary files for this article, located in the “documents” folder.

Table 3. Table of GitHub Repositories Containing NGS Pipeline Codes Processing Data at MMCI for the Data Catalogue.

NGS-data-FAIRification		
10.5281/zenodo.14237082		
Pseudonymiser	Organiser	Uploader
data-catalogue-pseudonymisation	data-catalogue-organiser	data-catalogue-uploader
10.5281/zenodo.14237042	10.5281/zenodo.14237004	10.5281/zenodo.14236863
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • data and information collection from multiple sources • data and metadata pseudonymisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • data cleaning • data organisation into meaningful structure • metadata extraction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • metadata centralisation • metadata upload to the data.bbmri.cz catalogue

5.3 Data Storage

Institute of Computer Science (ICS)® of Masaryk University provides a unique service called SensitiveCloud®, managed under the CERIT-SC® organisational unit. SensitiveCloud is a computing and storage environment for working with sensitive data in academic research, particularly life science and medicine. This service emphasises data security through robust technical infrastructure, processes, and policies. Based on the Kubernetes platform, SensitiveCloud offers high scalability to meet the needs of

® <https://github.com/BBMRI-cz>
 ® NGS-data-FAIRification: <https://zenodo.org/records/14237082>
 ® <https://www.ics.muni.cz/en>
 ® <https://www.cerit-sc.cz/infrastructure-services/sensitivecloud>
 ® <https://www.cerit-sc.cz/>

sensitive sequencing data storage, management, and processing. The usage of this service is formalised through a contract between MMCI and ICS MU®.

SensitiveCloud employs a straightforward file-based storage system, which organises files hierarchically for easy storage and retrieval. Data are stored in files within folders, which are grouped under directories and subdirectories. The filesystem is divided into several data blocks to avoid slow loading times when accessing multiple folders. These blocks are arranged to allow data access in two ways: by the year of sequencing or by the patient's year of birth.

We store our NGS data in the FASTQ format [38], widely accepted for data exchange between bioinformatics tools. Alongside this, analysed NGS data are stored in BAM and VCF formats [39] and are enriched with biobanking and clinical metadata. All these files are organised in a folder named after the pseudonym of the predictive number, which consists of a prefix "mmci_predictive_" followed by a unique alphanumeric code generated by a pseudonymisation script (see Chapter 4.3.3. *(Meta)data Pseudonymisation*). This folder can be accessed in two ways (see Figure 2):

- by the year of sequencing / sequencer name / run number / predictive examination folder;
- by the patient's year of birth / patient's pseudo-ID / predictive examination folder.

Note that data are not duplicated in this storage structure. Instead, the second access method links to the first, ensuring efficient and organised data storage without redundancy.

6. RESULTS

The main result of our work is the development of an automated data pipeline that processes and stores NGS data integrated with clinical and biobanking information with minimal manual intervention. Although our automated pipeline is designed for newly arising sequencing runs, we still have more than 7 TB of retrospective NGS data to be curated and adequately stored. Due to complications in obtaining analysis data from Velsera company, which analyses NGS data generated by the NextSeq sequencer, we performed results validation on NGS data generated by the MiSeq sequencer.

Given the presence of 3320 GB of retrospective NGS data generated by MiSeq between 2014—2023 (approx. 314 sequencing runs) and the acute shortage of storage space in the Department of Oncological Pathology, we prioritised addressing these existing data. Since retrospective NGS data at MMCI were stored on multiple hard drives in unorganised structures and only the Department of Oncological Pathology staff can collect all necessary files and provide library preparation details captured in a handwritten laboratory notebook, we agreed they would prepare NGS data packages, including analysis files, and manually upload them to the MMCI server. After this manual transfer, the automated pipeline handles the rest of the processes. It integrates NGS data with related clinical and biobanking information, extracts metadata, and performs data cleaning and pseudonymisation. The average original size of such

© <https://smlouvy.gov.cz/smlouva/22864021>

Figure 2. Filesystem Storage at SensitiveCloud Environment–Example of Naming Rules with Opened MiSeq Output.

a prepared data package was 36.7 GB per run. After the cleaning, the average size of a run is only 8.5 GB, which is more than a fourfold reduction in volume. In total, we processed 149 sequencing runs that were transferred into a secured cloud environment. However, the remaining runs could not be processed in the usual manner due to missing analyses and will therefore be stored without further metadata exposure in the catalogue. The data are organised within a structure that facilitates easy retrieval from the cloud storage.

From the OS perspective and value for the researchers is the development of a data catalogue utilising FAIR Genomes metadata schema available at *data.bmri.cz* the most visible result of our work. The data pipeline mentioned above concludes by publishing metadata into this catalogue. Only metadata of a complete NGS dataset, including patient consent for data reuse, were uploaded into the catalogue. Based on this restriction, only 91 records of sequenced samples from 149 sequencing runs were uploaded (each run contains approx. 12 sequenced samples). After authorization, researchers can browse the metadata within the catalogue. If interested, they can submit data access applications using the "Negotiate Access"

button (see Chapter 7.2. *Data Access for Applicants*). Since the selected cataloguing software-Molgenis-is compatible with the FAIR Data Point, after filling in the essential metadata, our catalogue naturally became a data point and enabled machines to search through our metadata.

In the case of newly generated data, electronic recording of sequencing library information into an Excel document is now implemented. This document automatically extracts data for the Sequencing Library module, ensuring adherence to standard predictive number formats. Consequently, managing new data is significantly more straightforward compared to retrospective data.

7. LIMITATION

7.1 Legal Aspects

7.1.1 Accessing Data Catalogue

Our data catalogue follows the BBMRI-ERIC authentication and authorisation privacy policy [40] and the Acceptable Use Policy of BBMRI-ERIC Services [41]. Users access the data catalogue using an authentication service called Life Science Login[®], which processes the user's personal data to identify the user. After identification, the potential user must accept the conditions listed in the Acceptable Use Policy.

7.1.2 Pseudonymised Metadata within Data Catalogue

When the user is successfully authenticated, authorised, and agrees on policies, he/she is allowed to browse pseudonymised metadata in our catalogue. Every record has its own universally unique identifier, while the mapping table is (in accordance with GDPR [42]) kept separately from data storage.

7.1.3 Broad Consent Concept for Biological Material and Data Reuse

The informed consent form is primarily intended for material admission into the Bank of Biological Material, which subsequently stores received material and provides it in case of a request from the scientific community. The patient's consent to use his biological material (residues gained during healthcare provision) for research is required by section 81 of the Czech Act on Health Services. It is an implementation of so-called broad consent [43], which enables giving consent for multiple potential future research projects by signing one form. A section of the consent form specifies that samples stored at MMCI may be provided in pseudonymised or anonymised form to external researchers. These researchers can request relevant patient information, such as gender, age, disease stage, treatment response, and other necessary details. However, the patient's identity must always remain concealed from the researchers.

Regarding data which are part of a patient's medical records, the consent of a patient with access to their medical records for research purposes is required by Act on Health Services [44]. Again, the concept of broad consent for future potential research projects is used. We must distinguish the consent

[®] <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/>

required by national law from consent for processing personal data under GDPR as a legal basis. Access to medical records requires the patient's consent. However, the secondary use of such data may be based on legal grounds other than consent, such as legitimate interest (Article 6(1)(f) GDPR) and scientific research (Article 9(2)(j) GDPR). The determination of an appropriate legal basis is based on a case-by-case decision. Data controllers in the Czech Republic may face legal uncertainty due to the absence of specific national legislation on processing personal data for research purposes. Based on our preliminary legal assessment, we believe that MMCI, as a healthcare provider established by the Ministry of Health for scientific research, is legally permitted to conduct research using legal bases other than patient consent. However, this interpretation may differ in other countries, where national regulations may impose different requirements. Consent is not considered an appropriate legal basis in certain types of health research, mainly where there is a clear imbalance of power between the data controller and the data subject (for example, the data subject–patient–is not in good health condition and is offered participation in research such as clinical trial) [45]. In case the processing of sensitive data is based on art. 9/2 letter j) GDPR, the data controller must implement appropriate safeguards. These safeguards are named demonstratively in section 16 of Act on Personal Data Processing [46] (including pseudonymisation, limitation of access to data, designation of Data Protection Officer, encryption, limitation of transmission).

7.2 Data Access for Applicants

To browse metadata or apply for access to data described within the BBMRI.cz Data Catalogue, potential applicants must sign in via the LifeScience Login to verify their identity. This measure helps safeguard sensitive metadata from unauthorised access. Upon their first visit to the catalogue, users must agree to the terms and conditions and create an account, which can be authenticated using their institutional credentials, ORCID ID, or by creating a username and password[Ⓞ]. Subsequently, the user must wait for their registration to be approved by the catalogue administrators. Once approved, the user can log in to the catalogue and start browsing metadata.

After successful authentication, applicants can utilize the Negotiator tool, accessible via the provided button, to initiate a data access application. Within the application, applicants are prompted to provide details regarding the project for which data access is sought, including intended data reuse, a description of the requested data, and, if applicable, information about a relevant ethics vote. Following submission, the application undergoes review by the Clinical Research Council and Ethics Committee. Applicants may be required to provide additional information about their research if necessary. Upon approval from both commissions, a Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) will be executed to ensure legal compliance and proper data handling practices. This agreement outlines terms and conditions for data transfer, including usage restrictions, security measures, and data-sharing protocols. Applicants are reminded to adhere strictly to the DTA's terms and declare their commitment to using the data solely for agreed-upon purposes, avoiding any misuse.

[Ⓞ] <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/version-2023/user/how-to-get-ls-id.htm>mapping table

8. CONCLUSION

Our work culminates in developing an automated data pipeline (see Figure 3) to seamlessly process and store NGS data integrated with clinical and biobanking information, requiring minimal manual intervention. Despite focusing on newly generated sequencing runs, we have also addressed the critical challenge of curating and organising more than 3 TB of retrospective NGS data from MiSeq runs collected since 2014. This consolidation was essential due to severe storage constraints in the Department of Oncological Pathology at MMCI. Initially stored across disparate hard drives in unstructured forms,

Figure 3. Detailed (Meta) Data Flows at Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute after Automation Processes Implementation.

these retrospective datasets were manually prepared and uploaded to the MMCI server. Our automated pipeline then seamlessly integrated these data, cleaned, described and pseudonymised them, resulting in a substantial fourfold reduction in data volume from an average of 36.7 GB to 8.5 GB per run. A total of 149 sequencing runs were processed and securely transferred to a secured cloud environment, organised for efficient retrieval within a structured framework.

In alignment with FAIR Principles, the key outcome of our efforts is establishing a data catalogue utilising the FAIR Genomes metadata schema hosted at *data.bbmri.cz*. The automated data pipeline concludes by publishing metadata into this catalogue, serving as a single point of data presentation. We upload only complete records of sequenced samples to the catalogue, with patient consent for data reuse being a prerequisite. Therefore, out of 149 runs (each consisting of approx. 12 sequenced samples), only 91 records were eligible for inclusion in the catalogue. To ensure clarity, we must emphasise that our metadata catalogue is indeed metadata-centric, containing descriptive information about the data rather than the data itself. Interested parties can apply for access to the data based on the provided descriptive details via the Negotiator tool. In summary, our approach resolves immediate data management challenges and lays a solid groundwork for advancing genomic research and facilitating broader access to valuable biomedical data resources.

At the time of writing this article, it was not possible to address every element of all the FAIR Genomes Metadata Schema modules. To ensure comprehensive coverage of all elements and potentially add more specialised modules (e.g., for whole slide image data), we are actively participating in the implementation of a new hospital information system and continuously refining the workflows we have already established. This is why the FAIRification presented in this work cannot be perceived as a one-time activity. Rather than that, it is an evolving process requiring regular improvements and responding to changes. Since our institute works with wide-spread Illumina tools, some steps within the procedure can inspire other biobanking institutions starting with FAIR NGS data management. In addition to continuously improving the whole pipeline, we would like to invite other Czech biobanks to share their NGS data via our metadata catalogue in the future. Thanks to FAIR Data Point, we would like to interconnect existing NGS metadata catalogues within the European biobanking community with our instance *data.bbmri.cz*. For European biobanks without national NGS metadata catalogues, we may provide the possibility to share NGS data via our catalogue.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data sets collected and curated during the current study are not publicly available due to their sensitive nature. However, their metadata are available within the data catalogue (available on *data.bbmri.cz*) developed as part of this work.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Data steward R.K. integrated the insights from molecular pathologists regarding sequencing data, expertise in handling sensitive information, and IT capabilities to design the presented pipeline. R.K. then wrote the manuscript with critical input and revisions from co-authors. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

Molecular pathologist O.H. played a pivotal role by sharing invaluable insights into the handling of sequencing data within the MMCI Department of Pathology. He elucidated Standard Operating Processes (SOP) and provided a comprehensive explanation of the entire data lifecycle, from the inception of sequencing data through analysis, processing, and subsequent storage.

Programmer T.H. implemented the proposed pipeline solution by programming it in Python and Bash. This involved pseudonymisation, data transfers, data cleansing, and other essential functionalities.

Programmer R.T. contributed to the architecture and design of the data pipeline and was responsible for integrating and deploying the Molgenis platform, thereby establishing the BBMRI Data Catalogue.

Our institutional legal officer, J.K., provided consultation on legal aspects related to the discussed topics and contributed to writing sections of the manuscript dedicated to legal considerations.

M. R., as a SensitiveCloud service owner, provided expertise in advanced environment design to process and store sensitive data there.

The IT coordinator, Z.D., contributed valuable expertise in managing sensitive data and provided guidance throughout the crucial steps leading to the development of the pipeline.

The supervisor of the main author of the article V.N. contributed significantly by assisting the author in writing the manuscript and guiding the methodical selection of technologies for the project.

Head of the Bank of Biological Material MMCI R.H. proposed the research problem, provided the biobanking data for integration and ensured resources for its achievement.

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LIST OF APPENDICES

- S1 (Supplementary File 1)–Mindmap of Sequencers Output: MiSeq (https://github.com/BBMRI-cz/NGS-data-FAIRification/blob/master/documents/mindmaps_of_sequencer_outputs/supplementary_file_1_Miseq_mindmap.png)
- S2 (Supplementary File 2)–Mindmap of Sequencers Output: NextSeq (https://github.com/BBMRI-cz/NGS-data-FAIRification/blob/master/documents/mindmaps_of_sequencer_outputs/supplementary_file_2_NextSeq_mindmap.png)
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